

Figure Ancstats. Fissidentaceae species phylogeny inferred using bayesian inferences from three loci trnA, trnl-F, and ITS. This phylogenetic inference is used for all ancestral character reconstructions. Nodes are labeled with node identity numbers referenced in Ancstats_Table.xls, associated with likelihood values for each character state at each numbered node. The scale provided indicates substitutions per site.